

Soil and crop management

Effect of crop residue on blue-green algae growth in wetland rice

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Field experiments determined the effect of crop residue on growth of blue-green algae (BGA) during 1981 summer and monsoon season at Tamil Nadu Agricultural University. Treatments with three replications were randomized in a split-plot design.

Summer treatments were control (S_0), 10 t rice long straw/ha (S_1), 4.6 t 30-cm rice stubbles/ha (S_2), and 10 t composted rice straw/ha (S_3) incorporated with 50, 75, or 100 kg N/ha alone and in combination with bonemeal (22 kg P/ha). The subsequent monsoon rice crop was raised in the same field to study the residual effect of residues and bonemeal. Nitrogen was applied at 50, 75, or 100 kg N/ha alone and in combination with bonemeal (11 kg P/ha).

At rice flowering stage fresh weight of BGA from the topsoil was recorded at four $50 \times 50 \text{ cm}^2$ quadrats in each plot and expressed in kg/10 m².

S_3 recorded the maximum BGA weight in summer. S_1 yield was similar. During the monsoon season, S_3 was superior to S_1 and S_2 . This natural BGA buildup was stimulated by crop residues,

Blue-green algal growth at flowering. Tamil Nadu, India.

which provided the raw material for BGA photosynthesis under flooded conditions. Although application of bonemeal significantly improved the growth of BGA in both seasons, BGA grew more during the

monsoon season than in summer. Growth was inhibited at 100 kg N/ha (see figure). BGA withstood dehydration during the fallow period between summer and monsoon crops. □

Effect of deep placement of nitrogen fertilizer on ratoon rice

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Deep placement of nitrogen fertilizer on rice seems to improve nitrogen utilization efficiency and increase grain yield. We tested the effect of deep placement on ratoon rice yield.

IR9784-52-2-3-2, identified as having relatively good ratooning ability, was grown in 10-liter plastic pots filled with finely ground Maahas clay soil that was mixed thoroughly with 75 mg N, 44 mg P, and 83 mg K per kg soil before potting. Two 12-day-old seedlings raised in trays were transplanted into each pot. Water depth was 2-3 cm for 3 days and then increased to 5-7 cm and maintained at that level until grain ripening. When 90% of the panicle had ripened, plants were harvested by cutting at a 15-cm height

above the soil. Four days later, nitrogen as urea was evenly broadcast on the soil surface around each plant or placed 15 cm beneath the soil surface with an injector (see table).

Different N levels and placement methods had a significant effect on grain yield. Nitrogen applied at 15-cm depth produced significantly higher grain yield than broadcast N. The higher grain yield from deep placement was due mainly to increased panicle number and plant vigor (see table). □

Grain yield and other plant characters of a ratoon crop of IR9784-52-2-3-2 as affected by different rates and methods of N placement. IRRI, 1981 dry season (av of 4 replications).^a

Rate and method of placement	Grain (g/plant)	Panicles (no./plant)	Field grains (no./panicle)	Sterility (%)	100-grain weight (g)	Nodal tillers (%)	Plant height (cm)	Plant vigor ^b	Grain-straw ratio	Growth duration (days)
30 mg N/kg soil broadcast	9.2 b	18 b	32	24	1.89	74.9	69.9	7 a	1.2	58
30 mg N/kg soil deep placement	10.8 c	19 b	34	18	1.85	76.9	69.2	6 a	1.2	58
50 mg N/kg soil broadcast	16.9 b	25 ab	36	21	1.88	80.5	75.6	2 b	1.2	59
50 mg N/kg soil deep placement	25.1 a	34 a	39	13	1.87	65.7	75.2	1 b	1.0	61
Control	7.6 c	16 b	29	19	1.88	63.9	88.8	8 a	1.0	58
F-test on planned comparison										
Control vs others	**	ns	ns		ns	ns	ns	**	ns	ns
Broadcast vs deep placement	**	ns	ns		ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns

^a In a column, means followed by a common letter do not significantly differ at the 5% level. ^b 1 = extra vigorous; 3 = vigorous, 5 = intermediate or normal vigor, 7 = less vigorous than normal, 9 = very weak and small.

Effect of different sources and levels of nitrogen fertilizers on rice grain yield

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A field experiment was conducted on a loamy sand soil (pH 8.3, organic carbon 0.55%, electrical conductivity 0.05 mmho/cm) in Gurdaspur District of Punjab State to determine optimum nitrogen source and fertilizer rate for irrigated rice. Calcium ammonium nitrate, ammonium chloride, and urea were applied at 60, 120, and 180 kg N/ha. Each was applied in 3 equal splits: before puddling, and at 21 and 42 days after transplanting. Farming methods recommended for the area were followed and grain yield

Effect of N levels and sources on grain yield of rice variety IR8, Punjab, India.

N (kg/ha)	Rice yield (t/ha)			
	Calcium ammonium nitrate	Ammonium chloride	Urea	Mean
60	4.3	4.7	4.8	4.6
120	6.3	7.0	6.9	6.7
180	6.9	7.8	7.3	7.3
Mean	5.9	6.5	6.3	
	No nitrogen = 2.70			
	CD (5%)			
	Level or source = 0.28; level × source = 0.46.			
	Control × treatment = 0.45			

was recorded (see table).

Increasing N level significantly increased grain yield. Ammonium chloride produced maximum yield followed by

urea and calcium ammonium nitrate.

Calcium ammonium nitrate was significantly inferior to ammonium chloride and urea. □

Evaluation of nitrogen availability indices for rice in alluvial soils

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Different methods of testing soil nitrogen levels and their relationship to rice yields in alluvial soils were evaluated in the greenhouse. Five 20-day-old PR106 seedlings grown in a nitrogen-deficient solution culture were transplanted into pots, each with 4.5 kg surface soil (0-15 cm), from 20 Punjab soil sites. Soil pH varied from 7.2 to 10 and electrical conductivity from 0.15 to 2.12 mmho/cm. Treatments of 0 and 100 ppm N as urea

Indices of available nitrogen and their relationship with rice plant parameters.

	O. C. (%)	KMnO ₄ -N	NH ₄ ⁺ -N	NO ₃ ⁻ -N	NH ⁺ + NO ₃ ⁻ -N	NH ₄ ⁺ -N ^a
			<i>Available nitrogen (kg/ha)</i>			
Range	0.07-0.78	62.7-207.0	5.4-81.5	3.1-75.3	8.5-156.8	9.4-100.4
Mean	0.44	128.5	25.5	34.5	60.0	46.4
			<i>Correlation coefficients (r value)</i>			
Control grain yield	0.473	0.649	0.132	0.228	0.196	0.515
Percent grain yield	-0.027	0.143	0.159	0.193	0.169	0.004
Control grain uptake	0.433	0.581	0.261	0.288	0.313	0.489
Percent grain uptake	-0.250	-0.100	0.317	0.144	0.263	0.127
Control total uptake	0.476	0.643	0.307	0.300	0.346	0.610
Percent total uptake	-0.050	0.132	0.349	0.190	0.304	0.170

^aAfter 72 hours of soil incubation at 40°C.